

Wettability Effect of Water-based Inks on the Quality of Flexographic Prints

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Abstract— This study explores the substitution of solvent-based inks with water-based inks in Flexographic printing, focusing on the influence of surfactants on ink wettability and print quality on polymer films. The effectiveness of ionic and nonionic surfactants as additives in water-based flexographic printing inks was investigated. The wettability is evaluated by measuring a droplet's surface contact angle θ . The results demonstrate a consistent decrease in both the liquid-vapor surface tension and the contact angle of the printing ink on hydrophobic substrates as the surfactant concentration increases. Notably, a steady state is reached when the surfactant concentration surpasses the critical micellar concentration by 3-5 times. The findings highlight the significant role of liquid-vapor surface tension in determining ink wettability and print quality. Enhanced wettability leads to the formation of a more uniform ink film, resulting in improved gloss and adhesion. For the desired print quality standards, the ink's surface tension should be at least 10 mN/m lower than the substrate's surface energy intended for printing. These findings provide valuable insights for optimizing water-based flexographic printing inks, offering guidance on the appropriate selection and concentration of surfactants to achieve optimal print quality and ink performance.

Keywords— Flexographic printing, Print quality, Surfactant, Water-based ink, Wettability

I. INTRODUCTION

Water-based inks have been increasingly used in different applications because they contain little or no volatile organic compounds, particularly in the packaging market. However, the water-based inks are incompatible with hydrophobic substrates (polymer materials), resulting in poor substrate wetting. The reason is that the surface tension of water is 73 mN/m, which is much higher than the surface energy of the polymer substrate, which is about 28 – 32 mN/m. Two ways have been proposed so far to solve this problem: surface treatment (substrate modification) or changes in the ink formulation (ink modification) [1]. The first method is complicated and is only effective for a short time before printing. Therefore, the second method is considered a more suitable solution. Studies in this direction focus on surfactants added to the ink as additives [2 - 6]. Surfactants enhance the wetting of aqueous solutions on hydrophobic surfaces by adsorbing at the liquid-vapor and solid-liquid interfaces. This process leads to a reduction in the interfacial tension of each interface. The wetting effect of surfactants depends on their type, structure, and interaction with the surface. In a study where nonionic polyoxyethylene surfactant solutions were examined for octa-decyl tri-ethoxy silane surface, a decrease in the contact angle was observed from 90° to 30° [7]. Similar wetting capabilities were found for acetylenic diol-based surfactants (Surfynol® series TMDD 0-30) [8] and Tergitol NP15 on lampblack. The absorption of dodecyl ethyl dimethyl ammonium bromide (C12(EDMAB)) at poly tetra fluoro ethylene (PTFE) and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) substrates decreases the contact angle from 75° to 40° [9].

In contrast, the effects of anionic surfactants such as sodium acetate, sodium dodecyl sulfate, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide, and n-decanoyl-n-methylglucamine on alkyl ketene dimer (AKD) surfaces are a significant increase of the contact angle [9]. In addition, it is noted that surfactants are primarily applied in the presence of other additives, which affect their ability to modify the interfacial properties. In the case of flexographic inks, the presence of alcohol and electrolytes (common additives) strongly influences the wetting behavior of surfactant solutions. Some studies documented the adsorption behavior of different alcohols at air-water as well as solid-water interfaces, resulting in changes in the wetting ability of solid surfaces in the presence of varying anionic [10, 11], cationic [12] and nonionic [13, 14] surfactant solution. The influence of high NaCl concentrations on the equilibrium and dynamic surface tensions of surfactant solutions was found by Mohsin J. Qazi et al. [15].

On the other hand, the presence of surfactants tends to increase the foam formation during printing, affect the ink transfer, and reduce the gloss of the ink film [16]. For this problem, some anti-foam agents are added. These substances have the negative effect of lowering ink adhesion [2]. All these make the selection of suitable surfactants and their concentrations for water-based inks to replace the solvent inks on polymer films challenging for scientists.

Surfactants play a crucial role in enhancing both ink stability and surface wettability. Still, their effects can vary depending on factors like surfactant type, concentration, and interactions with other ink components. Unfortunately, these effects are not always positive. They can negatively impact the visual and physical characteristics of the printed output, including color density, gloss, and ink layer strength. Additionally, certain surfactants directly influence ink viscosity, affecting flow properties and printability.

Numerous studies have investigated how surfactants influence the physicochemical properties of inks, particularly regarding wettability and rheology, with potential implications on final print quality [17]. However, the direct effects of surfactants on print quality are still relatively limited. Thus, comprehensive studies are warranted to understand better the role of surfactants in achieving optimal print quality. Such research should directly correlate surfactant usage with printed outputs' visual and physical characteristics, establishing a more explicit connection between surfactant effects and print quality outcomes.

Closing this research gap will provide valuable insights for optimizing ink formulations and improving print quality in diverse applications. Our study explores the wettability effects of different commercial surfactants in Flexographic printing inks. We evaluate how these additives impact crucial ink properties, including rheology and contact angle, and assess their influence on essential print quality parameters like optical density, gloss, mottle, and adhesion. This thorough investigation of surfactant effects on print quality aims to advance our understanding of water-based ink performance and enhance printing processes.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Materials

Pigment Blue 15:3 (Phthalocyanine Blue) was used for dispersion supplied by RAMDEV, India. The physical form is a blue powder. Dispersant PAT-ADD DA 103 is a product of PATCHAM Company, America. TEGO® Anti-foam 1488 is from Evonik Operations GmbH. Acrylic emulsion PEAGAR LS5023 is made by Koatsugas, Vietnam, nonionic surfactants Polyethylene glycol sorbitan monolaurate (Tween20) and Nonylphenol Ethoxylate (Tergitol NP9), and Anionic surfactant Sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) are supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.

B. Surfactant Solution Characterization

Aqueous solutions of the surfactants were prepared by diluting them to the desired concentrations. The equilibrium surface tensions (γ) of these surfactant solutions were measured at 27⁰ C with a De Noüy type apparatus SEO - Surface Tension Analyzer.

C. Characterization of ink rheology and surface tension

The original ink with a composition shown in Table 1 was prepared using the procedure presented in [6]. The modified ink samples were prepared by adding surfactants separately with the required concentrations using a mechanical stirrer for 10 minutes. The viscosity of these inks was specified by the flow time in a Zahn cup #4, according to an ISO standard. The measurements were taken at 27⁰C. The contact angle was determined on static drops deposited on an untreated solid surface plastic film (Biaxial Oriented Polypropylene - BOPP) using needles of 0.5 mm diameter. The drop shape was photo 15 s after the drop deposition with the Tangent method [4].

TABLE I
ORIGINAL INK COMPOSITION

Component	Description	Concentra. (wt.%)
Pigment	Phthalocyanine	15
Dispersant	Polycarboxylate	15
Resin	Styrene-acrylic polymer	20
Additives	Viscosity controller, defoamer, alcohol, etc.)	10
Water		40

D. Printing and Characterization of Prints

Laboratory printing was carried out by a handle Flexo-proof instrument (Figure 1) with the anilox roller line ruling of 300 lpi (TMI Machines, China). All parameters, such as printing speed, anilox roller, and printing pressure, were kept constant during the printing process to form unity ink layers with a thickness of about 5 g/m². In this series of experiments, the results are the mean of 5 measurements from 5 prints created from each ink sample.

Fig. 1. Flexo-proof instrument

Optical color density (D) is a standard means for numerically quantifying the tone's value. It represents the perceived density of color, indicating whether a color appears dense and filled or thin and airy. The optical color densities were determined using an Xrite digital swatch book spectrophotometer, DTP 22.

The print quality was also assessed based on the type of optical inhomogeneity known as print mottle. This parameter was quantified using the scanner method for image analysis and defined as the ratio of "variation" in lightness to the average lightness [18]. The average lightness was calculated from the lightness values of each pixel. The variation was determined as the standard deviation in lightness values for all the pixels in the image. For this study, the software utilized was ImageJ. The measurements of images were conducted within the measuring size of 30 mm × 30 mm.

Print gloss refers to the shininess or reflective quality of a printed surface. It measures the light reflected from the printed material at a particular angle. Gloss is an essential aspect of print quality, as it can influence the visual appeal, perceived color intensity, and overall aesthetic of the printed output.

The print gloss (in the gloss units, GU) was measured at the 60° geometry condition by a Picogloss (BYK-Gardner, Germany).

The printed layer's adhesion was measured using an IGT Crumpling instrument and a special tape according to the ASTM D3359 standard [19]. The tests were performed after printing for 24 hours. Adhesion quality was classified on a scale of 5 levels, ranging from GT0 to GT4, based on the percent of ink adhesion or ink removal from the substrate 0 %, < 5 %, 5 – 15 %, 15 – 35 %, and 35 – 65 %, respectively. The percent adhered ink was quantified by scanned image analysis of the tape strips (stuck onto white paper) using ImageJ software regarding the number of pixels in the scanned image and the total number of pixels that can be determined.

The adhesion values such as GT0 and GT1 are considered acceptable according to DIN ISO 2409. Results below the GT1 threshold are unacceptable adhesion quality.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Surfactant Solutions

Figure 2 illustrates the equilibrium surface tension as a function of surfactant concentration. The surface tension of pure water at 27°C was measured to be 70.89 mN/m. The critical micelle concentration (CMC) in the water phase was determined as the concentration at the intersection of two linear segments in the plot of surface tension (γ) against $\ln C$. For SDBS, Tergitol NP9, and Tween20, the corresponding CMCs were found to be 0.3, 0.5, and 1.0 wt.%, resulting in equilibrium surface tensions of 28, 31, and 33 mN/m, respectively.

Fig. 2. Surface tension of surfactant solution versus surfactant concentration

It can be learned that the changes of γ as a function of $\ln C$ have the same behavior for the investigated surfactants. However, the "effectiveness" of adsorption of various surfactants is different, as shown in the slopes of the linear part of curves in Figure 2. The effectiveness of SDBS adsorption at the water-air interface is higher than the others. SDBS has the lowest critical micellar concentration and surface tension value. Hence, this surfactant may be beneficial for the wetting process. However, since SDBS is an ionic surfactant, its wetting power depends on the interaction between its hydrophilic groups and the ionic or polar sites on the substrate. Therefore, its wetting property will probably change depending on specific substrates and inks.

B. Ink Properties

In this series of experiments, ink wettability as a function of surfactant concentration was investigated. The concentration range was between 0 and 5 CMC for all surfactants. The experimental data and results are given in Table 2. The images of static contact angles of inks on the substrate are shown in Figure 3.

TABLE III
 PROPERTIES OF INVESTIGATED PRINTING INKS: VISCOSITY (ρ), CONTACT ANGLE (θ) AND SURFACE TENSION (γ)

Ink sample	ρ (s)	θ (o)	γ (mN/m)
Original (O)	18.8	70.3	82.9
O + SDBS 1%	18.9	40.6	36.9
O + SDBS 2%	18.9	31.4	33.1
O + SDBS 3%	19.2	32.2	33.4
O + SDBS 4%	19.4	27.3	32.0
O + SDBS 5%	19.4	27.4	32.0
O + Tween 1%	19.3	47.2	41.6
O + Tween 2%	19.3	34.7	34.4
O + Tween 3%	19.5	28.3	31.8
O + Tween 4%	19.5	22.8	30.6
O + Tween 5%	19.6	22.4	30.5
O + Tergitol 1%	19.1	53.2	47.4
O + Tergitol 2%	19.2	47.2	41.6
O + Tergitol 3%	19.4	46.5	40.8
O + Tergitol 4%	19.3	46.1	40.7
O + Tergitol 5%	19.4	46.5	41.0

The addition of surfactants decreases the surface tension of the ink; therefore, an improvement in the wettability is found. Figure 4 shows that the contact angle and the equilibrium surface tension decrease with increasing surfactant concentration and reach unchanged values for all surfactants. The critical surfactant concentrations are about 1.5 %, 2.5 %, and 2.0 % for SDBS, Tween 20, and Tergitol, respectively, 3 – 5 times higher than the CMC of aqueous surfactant solutions. In addition, there is an irregular change in the natural equilibrium tension of surfactants. These results are connected to the adsorption of surfactant on the pigment particle interface, which removes the surfactant from the bulk aqueous phase. The surface tension decreases as surfactant concentration increases until surfactant concentration is enough to thoroughly absorb all particle surfaces and the liquid-air interface [20]. The removal of surfactant molecules to the interface and across liquid phases depends on the type of surfactants, resulting in the change of equilibrium surface tension [20].

For investigated inks, a little higher is observed than solvent-based ink surface tension (about 23 - 24 mN/m) [21] and surface free energy of typical untreated polymer films such as PP, PE, and PET (28 – 32 mN/m) [20]. Hence, the investigated inks cannot replace the solvent-based ink printed on untreated hydrophobic surfaces. However, for pretreated substrates with energy from 40 – 70 mN/m, the surface tension of all the investigated ink may be low enough for printing.

The contact angles as a function of the measured liquid-vapour surface tension for the investigated inks added with various surfactant solutions are presented in Figure 5. All the data points on a straight line indicate that $\cos(\theta)$ is proportional with $1/\gamma_{vl}$. This also means the surfactants do not change $\Delta\gamma = \gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl}$ and only the liquid-vapor tension determines the contact angle released from the Young equation [22]. This behavior was observed by Bijoyendra Bera et al. [23] for other hydrophobic substrates and surfactants. Hence, a given hydrophobic substrate has a $\Delta\gamma$, determined by the slope of the fitted line, which in our study is 28.3 mN/m. A possible explanation is that in the presence of surfactants, the solid-vapor interfacial tension changes as much as the solid-liquid tension so that the two contributions cancel out [23]. The equilibrium contact angle occurs for a droplet in equilibrium with a microscopically thin water film on the solid surface, known as the precursor film [23, 24]. The surfactant molecules move past the three-phase contact line into the precursor film, contributing to solid-liquid and solid-vapor tension changes. Hence, Both γ_{sv} and γ_{sl} depend on the surfactant concentration and the nature of surfactant adsorption. This result is confirmed in our study here.

Fig. 3. Drop shape of the inks with different surfactant concentrations.

Figure 4. Contact angle of investigated ink samples

Tween 20 has a more substantial effect on printing ink wettability among the three investigated surfactants. It might be attributed to the greater capacity of primary hydroxyl groups in the macromolecule for hydrogen bonding [4].

The addition of surfactants leads to an increase in the ink viscosity (see Table 1). This increase upon adding the surfactants may be due to network formation between the polymer molecules in the aqueous phase and the surfactants on the surface [25]. The order of increasing ink viscosity due to the addition of surfactants is SDBS < Tergitol < Tween20, which is in the same order of decreasing the effectiveness of adsorption and the contact angle of ink. However, all the surfactant types have no significant effect on viscosity.

Figure 5. $\text{Cos}(\theta)$ plotted as a function of $1/\text{liquid-vapor}$ tension of inks

C. Print Quality

The original ink and four ink samples with surfactant concentrations above the critical concentration were investigated for print quality (ink samples 0, 2, 8, 12) on the corona-pretreated BOPP polymer film (~ 41 mN/m). The typical images of prints are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Ink layers printed on the substrate

The surface tension of the ink is critical in its performance on the substrate. Ink samples with surface tension higher than the substrate surface energy (41 mN/m in this case) tend to result in uneven ink layers, pooling, or insufficient spreading on the substrate surface, similar to the original sample without surfactant addition. Conversely, inks with surface tension below 41 mN/m demonstrate improved wetting and better adherence to the substrate.

Table 3 shows the optical density values of the ink samples in the full-tone area. The standard deviations of print density for each ink sample indicate statistical significance, with an average standard deviation of 0.02 across all samples. Optical density is directly related to ink layer thickness, where thicker ink layers exhibit higher optical density. The ability of the ink to wet the substrate during printing determines the ink layer thickness, with better wettability resulting in thinner dried ink layers and lower optical density, assuming consistent ink distribution in the inking unit unaffected by additives. As ink wettability improves, color density decreases, regardless of the surfactant type (Figure 7).

TABLE III
PROPERTIES OF INK LAYERS PRINTED WITH THE INVESTIGATED INKS: COLOR DENSITY, MOTTLE, GLOSS, AND ADHESION

Ink sample	Surface tension (mN/m)	Color density (D)	Mottle (%)	Gloss (GU)	Adhesion (GT)
Original (O)	65.3	-	10.03 ± 0.32	48	4
+ SDBS 2%	33.1	1.61 ± 0.020	4.36 ± 0.030	59	2
+ Tween 3%	32.4	1.59 ± 0.019	2.44 ± 0.029	58	2
+ Tween 4%	30.4	1.48 ± 0.018	2.35 ± 0.026	64	1
+ Tergitol 3%	40.8	1.64 ± 0.022	7.23 ± 0.021	52	3

Fig. 7. Color density as a function of surface tension regardless of surfactant type and concentration

The mottle measurements further support the findings. The mottling value decreases as the surface tension of the ink decreases, indicating enhanced ink layer uniformity. However, the mottle does not change significantly at surface tension values below the surface energy of the printing substrate (Figure 8). This result is comparable to commercial inks printed on similar substrates, suggesting satisfactory uniformity [2]. To achieve a uniform ink layer, the surface tension of the ink should be lower than that of the substrate by approximately 10 mN/m.

Fig. 8. Effects of surface tension on print gloss and mottling value

The rate of ink setting and ink thickness influence print gloss. The print gloss increases with increasing substrate gloss at low ink levels, while at high ink levels, it is primarily influenced by the microroughness or shine of the ink film [26]. Adding surfactants to the original ink improves wettability, resulting in increased gloss values in the prints, as seen in Figure 8, where print gloss almost proportionally increases with decreasing surface tension.

Regarding adhesion tests, the effects of surfactants significantly enhance the stability of dry ink layers during the wetting process (Figure 9). However, according to the ISO standard, only the ink with the addition of Tween20 with a concentration of 4 % meets the adhesion criteria (the percent of ink removed in the adhesion test is smaller than 5 %). Additional improvement in adhesion may be achieved through surface pretreatment using methods like plasma to increase surface energy above 50 mN/m.

Fig. 9. Tape strips and prints from the ink adhesion tests

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of surfactants on the wettability of hydrophobic substrates through contact angle measurements. The findings demonstrate that ink wettability improves with higher surfactant concentrations, reaching a minimum surface tension value at a critical concentration approximately 3-5 times higher than the surfactant's critical micelle concentration. Enhancing the wettability of water-based inks can improve ink setting and overall print quality. It is worth noting that achieving satisfactory print quality requires the surface tension of inks to be at least 10 mN/m lower than the energy of the substrate, following established standards.

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